

THEORETICAL BASIS OF REDUCING THE HIDDEN ECONOMY

Tillojev T.A.

Assistant of the Department of Marketing, SamISI

Abstract. The article theoretically analyzes the concept of the hidden economy, its causes and strategies for its reduction. The hidden economy is considered a type of activity that is not included in official statistics, but has a significant impact on the economic life of the country. This article examines the main factors of the hidden economy, its negative consequences and advanced approaches to its reduction. It also discusses effective methods for reducing the hidden economy, including institutional reforms, improving the tax system and the development of the digital economy.

Keywords: hidden economy, informal sector, tax revenues, institutional reforms, economic growth, corruption, regulation, digital economy, labor market, public policy.

The existence of the shadow economy has a significant impact on the most important macroeconomic indicators, the activities and development prospects of enterprises. Without taking into account the shadow component, it is impossible to have an objective idea of the scale of the national economy, its sectors and the volume of entrepreneurial activity of enterprises.

In modern conditions, the shadow economy cannot exist without prices and hidden cash flows, therefore, its construction is based on hidden financial relations.

The problems of the shadow economy have become one of the most important problems for many countries of the world. Some types of hidden activities (drug trafficking, corruption, financing of terrorism) are recognized as a threat to national economic security, they are rightfully included in the global

problems of our time. Therefore, this topic is one of the most important and relevant.

On the one hand, this phenomenon can be characterized as multifaceted, rapidly changing and requiring constant changes in definitions and their explanations, on the other hand, the lack of a clear systematization and definition of the concept in the scientific community and other areas can hinder the development of coordinated assessments and approaches by state bodies to eliminate the negative consequences of this phenomenon.

In modern economic dictionaries, the shadow economy is defined as "the production, distribution, exchange and consumption of goods and materials, money and services that are not controlled by society and are hidden from state authorities" [1].

The shadow economy is one of the important factors that negatively affect the country's economic stability and the state budget. This article examines the theoretical aspects of the shadow economy, its types, forms, and ways to reduce it.

1. The concept and essence of the hidden economy. The hidden economy is a set of economic activities that are outside the control and accounting of the state. These activities usually include tax evasion, illegal trade, and concealment from official reports. The hidden economy can manifest itself in the following forms:

- Informal economy - legal activity, but not officially recorded (for example, unregistered labor).
- Illegal economy - economic activity prohibited by the state (drug trafficking, corruption).
- Shadow economy - activity that, despite being legal, is carried out secretly to avoid taxes or earn income through illegal means.

2. Theoretical approaches to reducing the hidden economy. Various strategies based on economic theory and policy are used to reduce the hidden economy. These approaches include:

- Institutional approach - reducing the hidden economy by strengthening state management and control mechanisms.
- Neoclassical approach – tax reduction and deregulation can lead to legalization of the shadow economy.
- Public-private partnership – development of incentive programs to legalize the shadow economy.

3. Measures to reduce the shadow economy. There are the following main ways to reduce the shadow economy:

- Tax reform – high taxes encourage the shadow economy, therefore, it is necessary to reduce the tax burden.
- Development of the electronic economy – making money flows transparent through the digitization of payment systems.
- Strengthening regulation and control – strengthening legislation and encouraging official accounting.
- Increasing the economic literacy of the population – informing entrepreneurs and the population about taxes and the legal basis of economic activity.

On the contrary, the shadow economy encourages the development of trade and intermediary, financial activities, as the sectors most prone to “shadow”. In addition, the spread of the shadow economy contributes to the increase in income stratification due to the enrichment of illegal and clandestine business entities. The level of income differentiation in Russia is already one of the highest: the incomes of the richest segments of the population are 16 times higher than those of the poorest. This is the case in developing countries with a high share of the shadow economy.

Thus, the problem of the shadow economy for the country has become a serious systemic problem of national security, which can be solved only by implementing a set of targeted measures in all spheres of state and social life. It is worth noting that the success of the fight against the shadow economy and

corruption can be achieved only with conscious mass support for this fight in society, and this can only be achieved when there is high trust in the state and authorities.

Conclusion. Reducing the shadow economy is important for ensuring state stability and economic growth. The shadow economy can be significantly reduced through well-thought-out economic policy, tax optimization, and strengthening control mechanisms.

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